

Questionnaire: Knowledge and Practices of Nurses Regarding Triage Management

Section A: Demographic Information

S#	Variable	Response Options
1	Name	
2	Age	<input type="checkbox"/> 20–29 <input type="checkbox"/> 30–39 <input type="checkbox"/> 40–49 <input type="checkbox"/> ≥50
3	Gender	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female
4	Qualification	<input type="checkbox"/> Diploma in Nursing <input type="checkbox"/> BSN <input type="checkbox"/> Post RN <input type="checkbox"/> MSN <input type="checkbox"/> Other
5	Years of Experience in Emergency Department	<input type="checkbox"/> <1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1–5 <input type="checkbox"/> 6–10 <input type="checkbox"/> >10

Section B: Knowledge on Triage Management

No.	Question	Response Option
1	Do you know Triage is defined as the process of prioritizing patients based on severity of illness?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
2	Does The primary purpose of triage in the emergency department is save lives.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
3	Do you know a patient with cardiac arrest should be assigned which triage category?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
4	Does The color code “Red” in triage usually represent Immediate/critical?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
5	Do you think all vital signs are essential in triage assessment?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
6	Triage should be reassessed periodically for patients waiting.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
7	Does The nurse responsible for triage should have specialized training in emergency care?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
8	Can Delay in triage lead to increased patient morbidity and mortality?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

Section C: Practices Questions in Triage Management:

No.	Practice Statement	Always	Sometime	Never
1	Do you assess patients immediately upon arrival to the emergency department?			
2	Do you follow the standardized triage protocol in your hospital?			
3	Do you practice all vital signs (BP, HR, RR, SpO ₂) to guide triage decisions.			
4	Do you prioritize patients based on color code and severity of illness/condition?			
5	I re-evaluate patients waiting in the emergency area at regular intervals.			
6	I communicate triage decisions clearly to the medical team.			
7	Do you attend any courses/workshops on triage management?			
8	Challenges faced due to staff shortages or overcrowding during triage.			
9	I usually document triage events accurately in patient records.			